

COMPUTATIONAL NEUROSCIENCE

Object recognition: The hard problem

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MIT in the 1960s stood at the forefront of a digital revolution. Led by many of the fields early giants —among them Robert Fano, John McCarthy and Marvin Minsky -- advances in computing were already ushering in a paradigm shift in technology and communication. John McCarthy had recently pioneered the Lisp programming language, Marvin Minsky and Seymour Papert were developing the "computational geometry" that would herald in decades of research in artificial neural networks, and for the first time, students and researchers enjoyed access to a central computer system with over a hundred access points across the university.

The rapid development of more powerful computers, operating systems, and programming environments culminated in 1963 at MIT with the launch of Project MAC, a DARPA-funded venture with the ultimate goal of developing a full artificial intelligence rivaling even human cognition. As a stepping-stone, one of the first projects was meant to be completed within a single summer: the creation of a functioning computer vision system (Fig. 1).

In spite of the great success achieved by Project MAC encompassing several decades of breakthroughs in AI, progress in computer vision languished due to the seemingly insurmountable challenge of object detection. Though dissecting the spatial frequencies and simple features of images posed little challenge, the AI Lab's vision system failed in detecting the boundaries and categories of objects in the visual scene, which

continues to be a central challenge in computer vision today.

Only a decade earlier, the physiologist Stephen Kuffler had begun experiments on the mammalian visual system that would lead neuroscientists to start tackling the same computational problems in reverse: How did our brains allow us to see? Using microelectrodes to record action potentials of single ganglion cells in the retinas of anesthetized cats, Kuffler quantitatively mapped the responses of ganglion cells to precisely controlled visual stimuli. As early as the 1930s, Haldan Hartline had recorded the output of single ganglion nerve fibers and discovered that ganglion cells could exhibit various response patterns to light flashed on a particular part of the visual field: so-called "ON" units spiked signifi-

cantly more in the presence of light shone at the center of the visual field, while "OFF" units were suppressed by light and had transient responses to a change from light to darkness (Hartline, 1938).

Yet like the early endeavors in computer vision, this pioneering work on the vertebrate retina hardly accounted for the complexity of human vision, and the neural mechanisms subserving our ability to identify objects in the world remain poorly understood to this day. Why have the computations underlying object recognition posed such a challenge for computer and neural scientists alike? At least two explanations come to mind. First, unlike the three dimensions needed to describe a simple visual stimulus in space, the categories of mental abstraction occupy an extremely

THE SUMMER VISION PROJECT

Seymour Papert

The summer vision project is an attempt to use our summer workers effectively in the construction of a significant part of a visual system. The particular task was chosen partly because it can be segmented into sub-problems which will allow individuals to work independently and yet participate in the construction of a system complex enough to be a real landmark in the development of "pattern recognition".

Figure 1. The 1966 report outlining the MIT Artificial Intelligence Group's planned summer project to develop computer vision.

high-dimensional space.

From the neuroscientist's standpoint, this makes it difficult to even identify stimuli that reliably excite a given cell. Second, the operations needed to achieve properties such as stimulus invariance from raw visual input (e.g., detecting a face as a face whether viewing it head-on or in profile) are highly nonlinear. By and large, the greatest advances in computational neuroscience and applied mathematics in general have relied upon linear systems theory. Thus, object recognition confronts

clear that our progress in either endeavor will require a fusion of the two seemingly disparate fields of artificial intelligence and computational neuroscience. This is evident when considering the current state-of-the-art in computer object recognition. The current record is held by a team at Google Research, who recently used a 9-layered artificial neural network to identify cats, human faces, and 20,000 other object categories via unsupervised learning implemented on a cluster of 16,000 computing cores (Le et al., 2012).

The most interesting aspect of this work, however, is the biological inspiration behind their computational algorithm: their network consisted of 9 layers of artificial neural populations trained to represent various features of the image (Fig. 2). Using a stacked network architecture featuring 9 identically organized layers, the team adjusted weights on the 1 billion connections between neurons so that image features were represented as efficiently as possible.

After training, object recognition was performed by identifying neurons that attained the most selective tuning for specific objects, such as cats and human bodies. Notably, object classifications were read out from the most selective units using the same basic methods neurophysiologists employ to characterize coding in real neurons. Indeed, their computational algorithm is based on four fundamental concepts of neural computation: local receptive fields associated with individual neurons, pooling of inputs across many neurons, divisive normalization or "gain control" to provide invariance to changes in stimulus contrast, and serial processing in successive layers to encode increasingly complex, higher-level features (Fig. 2).

Considering the development of object recognition from the dual perspectives of biology and artificial intelligence lends insight into our evolutionary history as a species and our technological future. The ability to categorize abstract objects in the world or distinguish among individual members of our species is central to our lives as humans, and was clearly critical to our ancestors' adaptation to the cognitive niche. Yet these capabilities appear limited to a few select branches of the evolutionary tree. Physiological evidence underscores the costs of these computations: in the macaque monkey (our close ancestor), the brain circuits believed to carry out object recognition and related processes account for over 150 million neurons, spanning over 10% of an already metabolically expensive brain.

But neither mathematical complexity nor metabolic constraints prevented natural selection from giving rise to the incredible power of our visual systems,

Figure 2. Diagram of the macaque monkey visual system. From the retina, visual information travels through the lateral geniculate nucleus of the thalamus and, after passing through cortical areas V1 and V2, is diverted into the "dorsal" and "ventral" processing streams. The large extent of the primate neocortex devoted to ventral stream processing (> 150 million neurons, over 10% of all cortical neurons) reflects the complexity of nonlinear transformations required for object recognition and other functions performed by ventral stream areas. Figure obtained from (DiCarlo et al., 2012).

us with computations that are both difficult to conceptualize and computationally intensive to implement.

Despite these challenges, both our understanding of object recognition in the brain and our ability to carry it out in silico are growing. Moreover, it is increasingly

Their network could be used to detect cat faces in random images from YouTube with 75% accuracy, and achieved 16% accuracy when identifying objects from a wider set of 20,000 object categories. Though these results may seem modest, they represent a 70% improvement in accuracy over the previous state-of-the-art.

and it remains a question of when our computational algorithms will attain the performance achieved by evolution. A slump in neural network research ensued after Marvin Minsky and Seymour Papert noted in their book *Perceptrons* that single-layer networks failed at fundamental nonlinear operations, but the field was reborn decades later when theoreticians began solving far more complex problems simply by stacking many network layers on top of one another. Training unsupervised networks to recognize images of cats on Youtube thus marks another humble yet pivotal step forward. These advances hint at the devel-

opments to come in both computational neuroscience and artificial intelligence, two emerging fields that can no longer proceed in isolation ■

References

- Hartline HK (1938) The response of single optic nerve fibers of the vertebrate eye to illumination of the retina. *Am J Physiol* 121:400-415.
- Hubel DH, Wiesel TN (1959) Receptive fields of single neurones in the cat's striate cortex. *J Physiol* 148:574-591.
- Hubel DH, Wiesel TN (1962) Receptive fields, binocular interaction and functional architecture in the cat's visual cortex. *J Physiol* 160:106-154.
- Kuffler SW (1953) Discharge patterns and functional organization of mammalian retina. *J Neurophysiol* 16:37-68.
- Le Q, Ranzato M, Monga R, Devin M, Chen K, Corrado G, Dean J, Ng A (2012) Building High-level Features Using Large Scale Unsupervised Learning. In: *Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Machine Learning*. Edinburgh, Scotland, UK.

GUEST ARTICLE

Why yes, your child should learn chemistry

Manosij Majumdar / Chemical Engineer

An article in the Washington Post by David Bernstein asks why his son, fifteen, is being taught chemistry in high school when it is not mandated by the state and is not likely to lead to a career as a scientist, as his son shows little interest or faculty in chemistry.

The question is a valid one. The conclusions Mr. Bernstein drives himself to are less so.

Mr. Bernstein is an executive at a non-profit organization and should be familiar with the folly of assaying the worth of an ac-

tivity solely by its ability to earn a profit. My first defence of chemistry would also serve just as well as a defence of literature, mathematics, economics or even Mr Bernstein's own subject, philosophy.